
Sustainable Development Policy as an Effort to Protect Social Ecology in the Toll Road Construction Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia

Ali Nurudin¹, Denok Kurniasih²

^{1,2}Public administration doctoral program, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Jenderal Soedirman University

ABSTRACT	ARTICLE DETAILS
<p>One of the new paradigms in development is that it is not only short-term oriented, but the development process must be built on the principle of sustainability. The concept of sustainable development is a new model for how development is viewed, not only in terms of material benefits, but also paying attention to the sustainability of the entire ecosystem in an area. Sustainable development policy, in principle, states that development is developed across generations, where current and future generations can still feel the impacts and benefits of development. Development must be seen not only from the perspective of material and physical standards but also from the perspective of impact and sustainability, both environmental and social. The toll road development policy in the Special Region of Yogyakarta is very comprehensive in combining infrastructure development patterns and the sustainability of the social and cultural ecology of the community. The toll road construction policy established by the Yogyakarta Special Province regional government must meet the main requirements of not separating social areas, separating economic areas, destroying productive land, and not destroying cultural heritage.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Sustainable Development, Social Ecological Protection, Community Cultural Protection.</p>	<p>Published On: 06 May 2026</p> <p>Available on: https://ijissh.com/</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of decentralization is the beginning of implementing community power at the local level in encouraging synergy between the central and regional governments in the development process. Where governance is no longer oriented towards government monopoly as a single actor, but the government becomes a community partner in carrying out the process of accelerating development both at the central and regional levels (Karjoko, 2022; Saa, 2024). It is hoped that the national development process currently being implemented will be able to accelerate growth and sustainable development. Increasing and utilizing regional natural resources and local potential will be able to support development in the long term (Ferrannini, 2021; Liu, 2024). The implementation of national development policies is an effort to accelerate development at the regional level which is directed towards building effective government and being a driver in empowering and strengthening the community (Niyitunga, 224). This means that the central and regional governments are expected to be better able to recognize opportunities to increase development with the resources and potential they have, through development in strategic sectors in order to reduce the gap between urban development and development in rural areas (Ruan, et.al, 2021).

National development which tends to favor urban development as the only reliable engine of development must be changed. The new paradigm in development must be able to provide space and access that connects regions (Hou et al., 2020). Development at the regional or rural level must begin to be encouraged in order to overcome the problem of uneven development. Regional development in areas at the regional level must be seen as an inseparable part of interconnected areas. This comprehensive and non-dichotomous understanding is important and fundamental in preparing regulations or rules of the game relating to national development so that regional synergy and balance occurs, especially by development actors at the regional level. Approaches to the development process at the regional level are often separated from national development policies (Yi Jiahui et al., 2021). This has resulted in an urban bias process, namely regional development at the regional level which was initially intended to improve the welfare of rural communities but has actually had the opposite effect, namely the sucking up of regional potential in terms of human,

Sustainable Development Policy as an Effort to Protect Social Ecology in the Toll Road Construction Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia

natural and even capital resources. Thus, the national development approach must remain aligned and connected with development conditions at the regional level (Sitanggang, et.al, 2022).

National development aimed at improving the community's economy is very fundamental. The national development process must have an impact on improving the welfare of society evenly. The main principle in national development must also pay attention to improving the economy, regional growth, providing employment opportunities and increasing infrastructure development to support economic activity and accelerate the pace of the regional economy (Liang, 2024). The acceleration of national development must also be balanced with the ability to mobilize strategic economic sectors and the potential of a region, both in terms of agricultural potential, services and tourism development (Adebayo, 2024). National development efforts must also not ignore the social ecological side, where development must continue to pay attention to the social and cultural progress of society, so that the pace of development can continue to go hand in hand with the social and cultural aspects of a region. Aspects of local wisdom which have been part of people's lives up to now must not be lost because of development factors that are solely for economic improvement (Primc and Erker, 2020). This means that the national development process must be built with a holistic and comprehensive paradigm so that the impact of national development has an economic impact but does not eliminate the social aspects of society that already exist (Xue Eryong et al., 2021).

One of the new paradigms in development is that it is not only short-term oriented, but the development process must be built with the principle of sustainability. The concept of sustainable development has become a new model for how development is viewed not only in terms of material benefits, but also paying attention to the sustainability of the entire ecosystem in an area (Artene and Duran, 2015). This means that in the sustainable development process, the main principle is long-term development that is capable of having a cross-sectional impact on the economic, social and cultural aspects of society. The concept of sustainable development in principle states that development is developed across generations, in.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative research method with a literature study approach. The library research research method is a technique for collecting data and information by reviewing, analyzing and synthesizing various literature that is relevant to the research topic, such as books, scientific journals, previous research reports, articles and other written documents that are very relevant to the topic being discussed. The sources used are various books and scientific articles related to sustainable development policies.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development is not only a change in physical structures or materials, but also involves changes in people's attitudes. Development must be able to bring progress to society beyond prioritizing material and non-material aspects (Sumaryoto, 2010). Development has quite varied concepts. In simple terms, development is a change in a better and more advanced direction than before. Development can also be interpreted as an idea to realize something that is aspired to in realizing a better and more prosperous life for a community or society (Safonov, 2022, Moustakas, 2020). Development also cannot be separated from efforts made to meet human needs by utilizing limited existing resources. One effort to realize community welfare is by building toll road infrastructure as a strategy for improving the economy, social accessibility and connecting between regions (Butar and Rahayu, 2023)

Infrastructure development has a very important role in the economic system. The better the condition of the infrastructure, the more influence it will have on improving the economy in an area. One of the infrastructure developments that is most often carried out in a country is the construction of toll roads, as a solution for uniting regions and efforts to accelerate the economy (Ferdini and Sulistinah, 2020). In several cases, the construction of toll roads in large urban areas and their surroundings does have an impact on many industries located around urban areas. The function of toll roads is to connect production centers with global markets. Therefore, to facilitate business activities, toll roads are an alternative to speed up the flow of distribution of goods and services between regions. The development of freeway or toll road infrastructure in a country can be used as a benchmark to determine the extent of a country's economic progress, both macro and micro. Apart from that, the construction of toll roads can also be used as proof of a country's readiness to welcome a civilization that is easy and fast in carrying out community activities in a country (Heru Kuswanto, 2023).

In the new paradigm, development is not only seen from the material and physical standards, but must also be able to look at the impact and sustainability both environmentally and socially. The construction of toll roads in Indonesia cannot be separated from the negative impacts it produces. The impact of toll road construction as a national project tends to ignore the sustainability of the curved ecosystem and the social conditions of the community (Yudi et al., 2021). Under the pretext of developing national projects, toll road construction often requires displacing settlements, converting agricultural land, and destroying historical and cultural sites of local communities. One example is that the toll road construction process in East Java Province which crosses archaeological sites and cultural sites must be affected. Furthermore, the impact of the toll road construction in Benoa Bay, Bali, must damage the ecosystem and marine biota and damage the mangrove forest area (Andika, 2023).

Sustainable Development Policy as an Effort to Protect Social Ecology in the Toll Road Construction Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia

Productive Land Protection Policy and Social Ecology in the Toll Road Development Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta

Agricultural land has a strategic role and function as a basic resource in land-based agricultural businesses. Land is a scarce natural resource because its quantity does not increase, but the need for land is always increasing. This is what prompted the government to enact Law Number 41 of 2009 concerning Protection of Sustainable Food Agricultural Land. This means that Law Number 41 of 2009 clearly states that the conversion of agricultural land is a threat to achieving food security and sovereignty for society. The existence of rice fields is very strategic so efforts and policies are needed to preserve them and expand the use of productive agricultural land in order to strengthen national food independence in the future (Yudi, 2021). Law Number 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management has indicated what components are needed for the implementation of sustainable development, both at the national development level and at the regional (provincial, district and city) development level.

In supporting sustainable agricultural development, the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Government has established several regulations in the form of regional regulations. Yogyakarta Special Region Province Regional Regulation Number 10 of 2011 concerning Protection of Sustainable Food Agricultural Land. This Regional Regulation regulates the area of productive agricultural land that must be maintained as Sustainable Food Agricultural Land covering an area of 35,911.59 hectares. The division is for land in Sleman Regency covering an area of 12,377.59 hectares, Bantul Regency covering an area of 13,000 hectares, Kulonprogo Regency covering an area of 5,029 hectares, and Gunungkidul Regency covering an area of 5,505 hectares. In an effort to realize Sustainable Food Farming Land Protection in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, it has been regulated in the Yogyakarta Special Region Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2010 concerning RTRW of the Yogyakarta Special Region Province, which establishes sustainable agricultural land protection areas whose provisions are contained in the Regional Regulation of the Yogyakarta Special Region Province Number 10 of 2011 concerning Sustainable Food Agricultural Land Protection.

In connection with the implementation of the national toll road development project that passes through the Special Region of Yogyakarta, one of the important points is that it must not disturb existing productive agricultural land. This is aimed at maintaining sustainable agricultural development and as an effort to maintain the livelihoods of the community, the majority of whom are farmers. The process of building a toll road that passes through the Special Region of Yogyakarta must not be detrimental in terms of environmental impact, sustainability of productive agricultural land and aspects of the social ecology of society. The policy of Sri Sultan Hamengkubuwono X as governor in the process of building toll roads in the Special Region of Yogyakarta must meet absolute requirements. The construction of a toll road that passes through the Special Region of Yogyakarta must not damage the environment and productive agricultural land so that sustainable agriculture remains for future generations.

Protection of food agricultural land is an inseparable part of regional spatial planning. For this reason, food agricultural land protection needs to be carried out by determining food agricultural areas that need to be protected. Food agricultural areas are part of the arrangement of rural areas in the district. Controlling the conversion of food agricultural land through protecting food agricultural land is one of the efforts to realize food security and sovereignty, in order to maintain food security and community welfare in the future. Apart from the policy of protecting agricultural productive land, Sri Sultan Hamengkubuwono The construction of a toll road that passes through the Special Region of Yogyakarta must provide economic benefits for the community, it must disrupt the community's economic area, it must not separate communities or divide an area. This means that Sri Sultan Hamengkubuwono The following is a general overview of the construction of toll roads in the Yogyakarta region which must be connected between regions. The following is a map of toll road construction in the Yogyakarta area.

The toll road construction plan in the DIY region has several plans. First on/off ramp Maguwoharjo. This access makes it possible to connect directly with the eastern ringroad, Jalan Solo to the south and Jalan Tajem to the north. Second, the UPN on/off ramp, based on the map points, is to the north of the ringroad or west of Jalan Nusa Indah. Access in and out of this toll road will later be connected to the ringroad and Jalan Nusa Indah. The three Monjali on/off ramps are to the north of the ringroad. The point is likely to be in the middle between Jalan Palagan and Jalan Kaliurang. This access will automatically be connected to the ringroad and the two roads. If the toll road is operational, tourists from outside DIY who use the toll road and are heading to the Kaliurang tourist area can go directly through this route. The four Trihanggo on/off ramps are at the Trihanggo intersection, the point is to the north of Ringroad. Apart from being directly connected to the road, this access is also connected to the Regency Road. This on off point is to the east of Junction Sleman. According to the planning, the toll road construction section in the Yogya region will be fully elevated or floating along the Ringroad. However, specifically for the Jalan Monjali intersection, it will be privileged with at grade because this point is a crossing of the imaginary line between Mount Merapi, Kraton Jogja and the South Sea.

4. CONCLUSION

Sustainable development is one of the stages of long-term development that must involve various stakeholders. A balanced development strategy is needed between economic aspects, social aspects and environmental aspects supported by good institutional aspects. In the sustainable development process, there are two dimensions in the concept of sustainable development, namely the time dimension which concerns what is happening in the present and the future, and the interaction dimension which concerns the

Sustainable Development Policy as an Effort to Protect Social Ecology in the Toll Road Construction Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia

social system of society. Sustainable development is the elaboration of two main important elements, namely development which aims to always develop potential towards better and more sustainable conditions which aims to build resilience and preserve the natural, social and cultural environment of society. As the policy of protecting productive land and social ecology carried out by the Governor of Yogyakarta is trying to continue to provide space for the central government to carry out national development projects, but must also continue to look at aspects of the sustainability of the community ecosystem. This policy is able to provide protection in order to realize sustainable development both in terms of agricultural sustainability, the environment and maintaining the socio-cultural environment of the community to remain intact.

REFERENCES

- 1) Artene, Cristian, Maria, and Duran, (2015). *The components of sustainable development - a possible approach*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 26(15), 806–811. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00849-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00849-7).
- 2) Andika, Ida Bagus Made Baskara, Cecep Kusmanab, I Wayan Nurjaya. *The impact of The construction of Bali Mandala Toll Road to The Mangrove Ecosystem at Benoa Bay Bali*, (2023). *Journal of Natural Resources and Environmental Management*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.29244/jpsl.9.3.641-657>.
- 3) Adebayo Waidi Gbenro, (2024). *Resilience in the face of ecological challenges: Strategies for integrating environmental considerations into social policy planning in Africa*, *Sustainable Development*. 2024;1–18, wileyonlinelibrary.com/journal/sd.
- 4) Butar, Herry Wilson, Ety Rahayu, (2023). *Dampak Sosial Dan Ekonomi Pembangunan Jalan Tol Mkt Terhadap Umkm Pasar Bengkel Kabupaten Serdang Bedagai*. [0.58258/jisip.v7i1.4118/http://ejournal.mandalanursa.org/index.php/JISIP/index](https://doi.org/10.58258/jisip.v7i1.4118/http://ejournal.mandalanursa.org/index.php/JISIP/index).
- 5) Bergh, Drews, and M. Van Der, (2017). *Scientists' views on economic growth versus the environment: a questionnaire survey among economists and non-economists*. *Global Environmental Change*, 46(August), 88–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.08.007>.
- 6) Budi Prihatin, Rohani, (2015). *Urban Land Misuse: (A Case Study of Bandung City and Yogyakarta City)*, dikutip dari <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/72820737/pdf-libre.pdf?1634976544=&response-content-disposition>
- 7) Ferdini, Anggia dan Sulistinah. 2020. *Dampak Pembangunan Jalan Tol Surabaya-Mojokerto Terhadap Kondisi Sosial Ekonomi Masyarakat Desa Bebekan Kecamatan Taman Kabupaten Sidoarjo*.
- 8) Ferrannini, Andrea, Elisa Barbieri, Mario Biggeri, Marco R. Di Tommaso, *Industrial policy for sustainable human development in the post-Covid19 era*, *World Development* 137 (2021) 105215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.105215>.
- 9) Hou, Yanliang, Ruyin Long, Linling Zhang, Meifen Wu, 2020. *Dynamic analysis of the sustainable development capability of coal cities*, *Resources Policy* 66 (2020) 101607, journal homepage: <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/resourpol>.
- 10) Heru Kuswanto, Erwahyuningrum, , Habib Adjie. *Problematika Hukum Penetapan Lahan Sawah Dilindungi (Lsd) Terhadap Pelaku Bisnis Di Indonesia*, *Jurnal bisnis dan manajemen*, vol 3 No 2, 2023.
- 11) Karjoko, Lego, I Gusti Ayu Ketut Rachmi Handayani1, Abdul Kadir Jaelani, Muhammad Jihadul Hayat,(2022). *Indonesia's Sustainable Development Goals Resolving Waste Problem: Informal to Formal Policy*. Journal homepage: <http://iijeta.org/journals/ijsdp>. Vol. 17, No. 2, pp. 649-658
- 12) Liang, Pan. (2024). *The Influence of Policy Investment on the Sustainable Development of Universities in Underdeveloped Regions: An Empirical Analysis of China's Higher Education Landscape*, *Sustainability*, 2024, 16, 8068. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su1618808>
- 13) Liu, Min, Thanapauge Chamaratan,(2024). *A sustainable framework for urban ecotourism development: A comparative literature review of policy and practices in Thailand and China*, *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development* 8(8), 7961. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i8.7961>.
- 14) Moustakas, Louis, Arda Alan Isik, *Sport and sustainable development in Botswana: towards policy coherence*, *Discover Sustainability* (2020) 1:5, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-020-00005-8>.
- 15) Niyitunga, Eric Blanco, Mahlatse Ragolan, (2024). *Beijing consensus diplomacy: A promoter or threat to Africa's pathway to sustainable development*, *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development* 8(10), 7425. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i10.7425>.
- 16) Oktiana, Ulfa Nur, Waluyo, Asianto Nugroho, (2020). *Pelaksanaan Perlindungan Lahan Pertanian Pangan Berkelanjutan Berdasarkan Regulasi Rencana Tata Ruang*, *Jurnal Discretie: Jurnal Bagian Hukum Administrasi Negara*
- 17) Prime Kaja and Renata Slabe Erker, (2020). *Social policy or energy policy? Time to reconsider energy poverty policies*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2020.01.001>.
- 18) Ruan, Fangli, Liang Yanan, Dan Wang, (2021). *Policy effects on the sustainable development of resource-based cities in China: A case study of Yichun City*, *Resources Policy*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.10214>.

Sustainable Development Policy as an Effort to Protect Social Ecology in the Toll Road Construction Process in the Special Region of Yogyakarta Province, Indonesia

- 19) Sumaryoto, (2020) *Dampak Keberadaan Jalan Tol Terhadap Kondisi Fisik, Sosial, Dan Ekonomi Lingkungannya*, Journal of Rural and Development.
- 20) Suparmoko, Muhammad, (2020) *Konsep Pembangunan Berkelanjutan Dalam Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional Dan Regional*. Jurnal Ekonomika dan Manajemen.
- 21) Sitanggang, Parlinggoman, Mella Ismelina F. Rahayu, (2022). *Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Lahan Produktif Pertanian akibat Maraknya Alih Fungsi Lahan Untuk Keperluan properti, Industri Dan Proyek Pembangunan Strategis nasional Berdasarkan Hukum Positif Indonesia*. Jurnal Hukum Adigama
- 22) Saa, Septinus, (2024). *Policy analysis of green bonds in Indonesia: Strategies for achieving sustainable development*, Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development 2024, 8(10), 6535. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i10.653>.
- 23) Salo, Hanna H., Annukka Berg, Kaisa Korhonen Kurki, Satu L'ahteenoja, (2022). *Small wins enhancing sustainability transformations: Sustainable development policy in Finland*, Environmental Science and Policy 128 (2022) 242–255, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.11.024>.
- 24) Safonov, Yuriy, Alla Abramova, Dmytro Kotelevets, Oleksandr Lozychenko, Oleksandr Popov, Suhail Zayed Hamad Khamis Almazrou, (2022). *Analysis of Regulatory Policy in the Context of Sustainable Development of Eastern European Countries*, International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning.
- 25) Ustymenko, Volodymyr, Olena Zeldina, (2019). *EU Investment Policy as the Basis for Sustainable Development: Implementation Prospects in Ukraine*, European Journal of Sustainable Development (2019), 8, 1, 40-52, Doi: 10.14207/ejsd.2019.v8n1p40.
- 26) Xue Eryong, Jian Li, and Xingcheng Li, (2021). *Sustainable Development of Education in Rural Areas for Rural Revitalization in China: A Comprehensive Policy Circle Analysis*, Sustainability, 2021, 13, 13101. <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability>.
- 27) Yi Jiahui, Sheng Dai, Jinhua Cheng, (2021). *Qiaosheng Wu, Kailei Liu Production quota policy in China: Implications for sustainable supply capacity of critical minerals*, Resources Policy 72 (2021) 102046, journal homepage: <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/resourpol>.
- 28) Yudi, Permai, Lyndon Parulian Nainggolan, Bobby Sutra Saragih, (2021). *Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Lahan Perkebunan Dan Pertanian Masyarakat Akibat Terjadinya Alih Fungsi Lahan*, Justitia/Vol.03/No. 02.